

8 Theory and The Equivalence Principle In Quantum Scale

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Abstract:

By using the new framework of the 8-theory, an analysis of Gravitation and acceleration can be created for fermions. Such an analysis will expend the Einstein equivalence and allow us to understand how the equivalence is manifested in quantum scales. The equivalence is already given in the main equation of the theory. However, since 8-theory also has within its scope fermions and bosons, the question of quantum gravity can be now viewed in a new way. Reader is assumed to have read the thesis as one will not elaborate on the development of those equations in this paper.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (0)$$

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial t} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \quad (1.2)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.21)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

Suppose the matrix has a fermion that is an arbitrary variation of the manifold given by the term $\delta g = 0$. What would be the consequence? Given by equation (2) the arbitrary variation will cause the matrix to accelerate outward. That is in complete agreement of Einstein theory of gravitation, equation (2) implies:

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial \delta g'}{\partial t} \quad (5)$$

Since the matric varied due to the arbitrary variation, which appeared in it, and in particular, it expended outward, the distance increased. Suppose the quark was conscious and could perform measurement, its very existence affected the matric, and the time in which a boson field will need to reach the object measured has increased because of the quark manifesting.

In special relativity, the great Einstein used velocity, but here there is no velocity. There is no such thing velocity in the 8 theory. The quark may conclude that the object is moving, but what is happening is that the matric itself is varying, because of that quark.

We also have in this framework the invariance of the speed of light, given by the coupling constant equation, and the fact that the propagation process is similar in all interactions.

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (6)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (7)$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (8)$$

General relativity implies an equivalence relation between curvature and acceleration. 8 theory implies that as well, but also in addition implies that curvature will **cause** outward acceleration of the matric by (1). Einstein had to add the cosmological constant in an artificial way, but here it's the main equation. Such a condition than allow us to understand relativity in a new and elegant way. C is invariant, and every arbitrary variation of the manifold causing an outward acceleration of the matric, the matric itself varying in such way that those arbitrary variations will eventually measure different distances and times. The entire theory of Einstein is contained in just one equation.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)